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Performance Characteristics of African Catfish Fingerlings, (Burchell, 1822) Fed with Diet Mixed with Processed Garlic (*Allium sativum*)

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Abstract

Performance characteristics of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings fed with diet mixed with processed Garlic (*Allium sativum*) was carried out. Two hundred and twenty five (225) *C. gariepinus* fingerlings (mixed sex) with average initial weight of 7.8 ± 0.5 g were treated with five diets. 15 *C. gariepinus* fingerlings per glass tank (0.9m x 0.45m x 0.45m in dimension) with three replicates per treatment were reared for 12 weeks. Five experimental diets were formulated, four of these contained processed Garlic at varying level of inclusion, 0% (control experiment), 2.5%, 5%, 7.5% and 10% respectively. Result shows that, there was no significant difference ($P \geq 0.05$) in all the treatments in terms of mean weight gain, feed intake, feed conversion ratio and specific growth rate. The fish on diets 1 (0%) had the highest feed conversion ratio, highest weight gain and the highest feed intake this perhaps might be due to absence of processed Garlic with its attendant pungent characteristics smell in the diet. Processed Garlic (*Allium sativum*) is thus not recommended in the diet of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings unless the pungent smell is removed by processing before adding to fish feed.

Key Words: Performance characteristics, *Clarias gariepinus*, fingerlings, Garlic

Introduction

Aquaculture practices are one of the ways of augmenting the importation of fish in order to meet the high consumption capacity of our teeming population. Nonetheless, in the recent past, rearing of fish in enclosures under captivity has faced the greatest challenges of feed ingredients which either scarce or expensive. Eyo, (1990) and FAO, (2008) reported that the cost of feeding fish amounts to over two thirds of the operating cost of a fish culture in an intensive system. Cost of feeding is usually high in intensive aquaculture which is about 60-75% of the operating cost especially in the intensive culture of fish in which the fish are fed artificial feeds, therefore, the need to source for artificial feeds, based mainly on feed with ingredients of plant origin which are less expensive and can produce comparable results are important.

Inclusion of plant leaf meal in the diet of fish as reported by Citarasu *et al.*, (2001 and 2002), and Sivaram *et al.*, (2004) are known to induce anti-stress, promote growth enhancement, serves as appetite stimulant and immune-stimulation in aquaculture practices but dietary nutrients are essential for the farming of aquatic organisms. The nutritional value of a dietary ingredient is in part dependent on its ability to supply essential nutrients for normal fish growth and health which are not often synthesized by fish and must be supplied in their diet (You *et al.*, 2006).

Some plants are natural sources of safer and cheaper leaf meal for livestock, therefore the development of formulated feeds which satisfy the nutritional requirements of the fish is considered to be one of the major tasks in aquaculture (Degani *et al.*, 1989) much research is therefore directed towards the development of minimum cost of feeds to rear the fish to marketable sizes.

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Common Garlic (*Allium sativum*) as described by Encarta (2008) is a horticultural crop having characteristics strong odor and sharp taste which is covered with a papery skin. Garlic originated from Asia Minor and spontaneously grows in southern Europe and it belongs to the family, Liliacea. Garlic is rich source of calcium, phosphorus and vitamin B1; it has a high content of carbohydrates and as a consequence, a high nutritive value. Garlic also contains iodine salts which have a positive effect on the circulatory system and sulphur salts with positive effects on the skeletal system, cholesterolemia, and liver diseases. Garlic also contains vitamin B-complex, vitamins A and C (Tremblay, 2018)

Fish growth and development is a function of good management practices therefore, the aim of this feeding trial is the use of garlic in fish feed formulation as an appetite stimulant whether it will enhance their growth indices.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The study was conducted in the fish rearing unit of Fisheries Technology Department, Lagos State Polytechnic, Ikorodu, Nigeria.

Two hundred and twenty two (225) *Clarias gariepinus* mixed sex fingerlings with average initial weight of 7.8 ± 0.5 g sourced from fish hatchery unit of the Fisheries Technology Department were used. Locally sourced feed ingredients were also used in formulating feed. Weighing scale (Ohaus Scout Pro Balances Model Sp-601), fresh water from overhead tank, aerator machine and its accessories, hand net, pH meter, thermometer and DO meter from water kit suit (Ezdo Model PCT-407) were used for measurement of weight and water quality characteristics respectively. The experiment was laid out in 15 units of rectangular glass tanks with the dimension of 0.9m x 0.45m x 0.45m each.

The glass tank are five in number and each tank is partitioned into three compartment representing 1 treatment and 3 replicates each with total number of 15 units. 225 mixed sex fingerlings of *Clarias gariepinus* that have undergone starvation therapy for 24hours were allotted randomly into each unit with 15 fingerlings per unit. 5 treatments with 3 replicate each and a control experiment.

Five (5) Kilograms of experimental diet was formulated for the five treatments which include maize, Fishmeal, Garlic, Bone meal, Vitamins and Mineral Premix and salt were purchased from a local market in Ikorodu, Lagos State except the grinded garlic which was purchased from reputable departmental store in town with brand name "Aged Black Garlic" manufactured by 'Think Remedy Company'. The powdered garlic was mixed with other feed ingredients to formulate the diets (pellets) at 0%, 2.5%, 5.0 %, 7.5% and 10% levels of inclusion representing diet 1, diet 2, diet 3, diet 4, and diet 5 respectively as shown in Table 1.

Clarias gariepinus fingerlings were fed based on 5% body biomass and the quantity of the food are adjusted fortnightly based on the weight gained. The ration fed is usually portioned into two equal halves and fed between 7.00hours and 16.00hours for 12 weeks. The uneaten food and fecal materials are siphoned out when water are not due for changing. The water used in culturing is replaced twice a week with freshwater from overhead tank in the hatchery house. The essential water quality parameters such as temperature, dissolved oxygen and pH of the aquaria glass tank were adequately monitored.

The following growth evaluation parameters were investigated; Mean Weight Gain (WG) = Final weight- Initial weight, Specific Growth Rate = final weight-initial weight/days x100
Feed Conversion Rate (FCR) = Total feed (g)/Wet Weight gain (g), Protein Efficiency Ratio (PER) = Wet weight gain/protein fed, Feed intake and Survival rate (SR) % = No. of fish/no of dead fish x 100. These were taken weekly based on the weight gained and amount of feed fed per body weight. The weighing of fish are usually done in the morning hours before feeding and the performance characteristics computation are carried out according to Amoah (2012) procedures.

Data Collection and Analysis: The experiment was conducted for 12 weeks using complete randomized design (CRD) where each treatment was randomly replicated with fifteen fingerlings of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings and the data generated was analyzed using 2-way Anova (Duncan, 1995).

Table 1: Composition of the experimental diet for *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings

Ingrédient	Diet. 1 (0%)	Diet 2 (2.5%)	Diet. 3 (5.0 %)	Diet.4 (7.5%)	Diet.5 (10%)
Maize	37.5	37.5	37.5	37.5	37.5
Fish meal	11.2	11.2	11.2	11.2	11.2
Soy-meal	31.25	31.25	31.25	31.25	31.25
Garlic	0.00	0.25	0.5	0.75	1.00
Bone meal.	0.40.	0.40	0.40.	0.4.	0.4
Lysine.	0.10.	0.10.	0.10.	0.10.	0.10
Methionine.	0.10.	0.10.	0.10.	0.10.	0.10
Premix	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
Vitamin .	0.10.	0.10.	0.10.	0.10.	0.10
Salt	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25

Calculated Analysis

Crude protein	28.90	28.90	28.90	28.90	28.90
Metabolizable energy (Kcal/kg)	256.38	256.38	256.38	256.38	256.38

RESULTS

Table 2 shows the Growth performance characteristics of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings fed with diet mixed with processed Garlic. The statistical analyses show that there was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in the weight gain among all the treatments but food conversion ratio was significant at 5% level. Table 3 shows the average weekly values of essential physico-chemical parameters during the experimental period. There was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) among all the treatments. The water quality parameters were measured to be in the range of tolerance for *Clarias gariepinus*. Dissolve oxygen ranged between 5.11- 5.13mg/l, Temperature 28.55°C - 28.59 °C and pH of 5.19 – 5.79.

Table 2: Feeding trial on *C. gariepinus* fingerlings fed with diet mixed with Garlic

Parameter	Diet1	Diet 2	Diet 3	Diet 4	Diet 5
Number of weeks	12	12	12	12	12
Initial Mean Weight (g)	7.92	7.88	7.89	7.96	7.93
Weight Gain (WG) (g)	5.64	5.50	5.49	5.45	4.88
Feed intake (g)	7.75	5.10	5.10	4.99	3.56
Feed conversion ratio	1.37	0.93	0.93	0.92	0.73
Specific growth rate (% per day)	0.080	0.079	0.078	0.077	0.069
Protein efficiency ratio	0.195	0.190	0.189	0.188	0.168
Survival rate (%)	95	90	85	81	65

Table 3: Mean values of essential water quality characteristics

Parameter	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
pH	5.73	5.68	5.78	5.19	5.79
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	5.11	5.13	5.12	5.13	5.11

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Temperature (°C) 28.59 28.60 28.55 28.60 28.58

DISCUSSION

Fish growth and development is a function of good management practices especially when good qualities of feed are used. However, many factors could influence the extent to which feed is utilized by the fish such as environment, temperature, quietness, amount of darkness, space, availability of water, the presence of disease, weather change, disturbance aggression due to mixed stocking and age (Cruz. 1996)

Utilization of processed garlic as a plant based nutritional additives in the diet of *Clarias gariepenius* fingerlings aim at stimulating the appetite to increase feed consumption for an increased production output within a very short period, however, the performance characteristics as shown in Table 2 shows that the inclusion of processed garlic could not achieve this aim. The 0% inclusion of processed garlic performs better than all other diets in the experiment. This disagreed with the report of Babalola *et al.*, (2016) on the nutritional advantage of using plant based ingredient in the diet formulation of *Clarias gariepenius* fingerlings

The nutritional composition of the formulated diet indicated that all the experimental diets had the same crude protein and metabolizable energy but different levels of inclusion of processed garlic, this perhaps may be responsible for the insignificant difference in the weight gain and specific growth rate in all the experimental diets. Although garlic, according to Dragan, (2007) and Gruenwald (2004) is a plant based product known to contain some minerals and vitamins for fish that enhances growth by stimulating appetite in aquaculture practices but its bioavailability in the diet could be hampered by the presence of anti-nutritional factors (Ansuman *et al.*, 2013) Also, NRC, (1981) and Pompa, (1982) as cited by Francis *et al.*, (2001) reported that high concentration of processed garlic in the diet could serve as an anti-nutritive factor which could block the biochemical pathway of protein metabolism in the fish.

The high survival rate in the experiment could be as a result of Garlic being a phyto-additives and antimicrobial agents in fish feed as reported by Gruenwald (2004)

The positive correlation between the weight gain and percentage inclusion of processed garlic in the diets could be attributed to strong characteristics odor emanating from the increase in percentage inclusion of garlic in the feed which could be nauseating to the fish, this shows that the higher the percentage inclusion the stronger the odor in the feed. This agreed with the report of Agbebi *et al.*, (2013) on the effect of dietary garlic source on fish feed utilization.

The fishes in diet 1 had the highest feed intake as compared with other fishes in the other experimental diets this may be due to absence of processed garlic in diet 1 which is known to possess strong characteristics pungent smell and taste with a papery skin cover as described by Encarta, (2008) that can possibly make the feed unpalatable to the fish.

The mean values of water quality characteristics recorded during the experiment falls within the range recommended for fresh water fish culture (Erondu, 1993). This perhaps may also be one of the factors responsible for high survival rate (Babalola and Fiogbe, 2017).

The fish on diets 1 had the highest feed conversion ratio. Hypothetically, this shows that fish in diets required 1kg of feed to obtain 1.37kg of flesh as described by Faleye and Oloruntoyin (1998) on feed conversion ratio of the diet fed to the fishes

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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The inclusion of processed garlic in the diet of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings shows that there was no significant difference ($P>0.05$) in weight gain, feed intake and feed conversion ratio. The result obtained shows that garlic can be conveniently used as a stimulant in the feed of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings if further processing can be used to remove ant nutritional factors in it as well as peppery and pungent smell

REFERENCES

- i. Agbebi O, Ogunmuyiwa T.G, Herbert S,M (2013). *The effect of dietary garlic source on feed utilization, growth and Histopathology of the African Catfish (clarias gariepinus)*. J Agric, Vol. 5, Issues 5, 2013 ppr. 26-34
- ii. Amoah, Y.T.(2012). *Effect of dietary protein levels on growth and protein utilization in juvenile arctic char(Salvinus alpinu)*. United Nations University Fisheries Training Programme, Iceland [final project]. <http://www.unuftp.is/static/fellows/document/yaal1prf.pdf>
- iii. Ansuman Hajra, Anupriya Mazumder, Anjali Verma, Debi Prasad Ganguly, Bimal P. Mohanty and Anil P. Sharma (2013). *Antinutritional factors in plant origin fish feed ingredients: the problems and probable remedies*. Advances in Fish Research, Vol.V, Pages 193–202 Edited by : U.C. Goswami, Narendra Publishing House, Delhi, India
- iv. Atanda A.N. (2012). *Fish species diversification in aquaculture for the success of the agriculture transformation agenda: the role of tilapia production*. A paper presented at 2012 Annual public Lecture of the Fisheries Society of Nigeria (FISON), 21pp
- v. Babalola O.A, Onigemo M.A and Okochi A.N (2016): *Growth Response of Oreochromis niloticus Fingerlings fed with fermented Parkiabioglobosa diets*. Journal of Aquatic Sciences 31(2B):365-372.
- vi. Babalola, O.A and Fiogbe D.E (2017): *Hydrology and Heterogeneous Distribution of Water Quality Characteristics in the Complex Porto-Novo Lagoon Ecosystem* Journal of Aquatic Sciences 32 (1B): 145-158.
- vii. Citarasu, T., R. R. Sekar, M. M. Babu and M. P. Marian.(2001). *Developing Artemia enriched herbal diet for producing quality larvae in Penaeus monodon*. Asian. Fish. Sci. 15:21-32.
- viii. Cruz PS. (1996). *Feed quality problems and management strategies*, pp. 64-73. In: Santiago CB, Coloso RM, Millamena OM, Borlongan EG (eds) *Feeds for Small-Scale Aquaculture*. Proceedings of the National Seminar-Workshop on Fish Nutrition and Feeds; SEAFDEC Aquaculture Department, Iloilo, Philippines
- ix. Degani T, Tomasz P, Franciszek P, (1989) *Biological and economical evaluation of African and European catfish rearing in water recirculation systems*
- x. Duncan (1955) *A methodological Analysis of Segregation Indexes*
- xi. Encarta (2008): *Characteristic nature of garlic and the constituents*. <http://Encarta.com/2008>
- xii. Erondu, Es., Nubian, C. & Nwadu, O (1993). *Haematological studies on focus catfish species raised on fresh water ponds in Nigeria*. Journal of pure and Applied technology. 9: 250-256
- xiii. Eyo, A.A (1990) *Growth Responses and Nutritional Evaluation of Cassava Peel Based Diet on Tilapia (Oreochromis niloticus) Fish Fingerlings*. Journal of Food Technology 6 (5): 207-213, ISSN: 1684-8462
- xiv. Falaye, A.E. and Oloruntuyi, O.O.(1998). *Nutritive Potential of plantain peel meal and replacement value for maize in diet of African catfish (Clarias gariepinus) fingerlings*. Trop. Agric (Trinidad), 75, (4), 488-492
- xv. FAO. (2008). *The State of the World Fisheries*. Food and Agriculture Organization, Rome, Italy 230pp.
- xvi. Francis, George., Makkar, Harinder and Becker, Klaus. (2001). *Antinutritional factors present in plant-derived alternate fish feed ingredients and their effects in fish*. Aquaculture. 199.197-227. 10.1016/S0044-8486(01)00526-9.
- xvii. Gruenwald, J., (2004). *PDR for Herbal Medicines 3rd Edn*. Montvale, NJ: Thomson PDR

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- xviii. Sofia M.J. (2006). *Impact of aquaculture on water resources*. In: Brune, D.E and Tomaso, J.R(Eds). *Advances in world aquaculture*, 3, 565-591.
- xix. Sivaram, V., M. M. Babu, T. Citarasu, G. Immanuel, S. Murugadass and M. P. Marian.(2004). *Growth and immune response of juvenile greasy groupers (Epinephelus tautoga) fed with herbal antibacterial active principle supplemented diets against Vibrio harveyi infections*. *Aquaculture* 237:9-20.
- xx. Tremblay,, Sylvie. (2018) "Which Vitamins Does Garlic Have?" *Healthy Eating | SF Gate*, <http://healthyeating.sfgate.com/vitamins-garlic-have-5598.html>. Accessed 02 August 2018.
- xxi. You W.C, Brown L.M, Zhang L, Li J.Y, Chang Y.S, Ma J.L, Pan K.F, Liu W.D, Crystal-Mansour S, Pee D, Blot W.J, Fraumeni J.F, Xu G.W (2006). *Randomized double blind factorial trial of three treatments to reduce the prevalence of precancerous gastric lesions*. *Natl Cancer Inst*, Jul 19; 98(14):974-83